

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

BigDataForAll

Promoting Statistics and Big Data through Gamification and Digital Education

#BIGDATAFORALL

2021-2023

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

Context

Partners

**The University of
Salamanca**
(USAL) - Spain

**Biderbost,
Boscan
& Rochin**
(BB&R) - Spain

**Rosto
Solidário**
(ROSTO) - Portugal

ODISEE
Belgium

**STIFTELSEN
HOGSKOLAN I
JONKÖPING**
(SHJ) - Sweden

PARTNER LOCATION

Objectives

Update professors/ professionals' competences on how **to design, implement and evaluate gamification processes** for teaching (in general), especially Statistics and Big Data (in particular) through a MOOC.

Connect Universities with SMEs/NGOs that require personnel with knowledge and skills in Statistics and Big Data, so that between these actors they jointly develop an educational itinerary through a gamification process (digital game) that responds to this need.

Update Statistics and Big Data competences to students/youth through the previous gamification process (digital game), so that they **increase their chances of insertion into the labour market** (connecting them with SMEs/NGOs that require personnel with these knowledge / skills)

Provide **innovative practices** to the educational, youth, training, business and social sectors so that they can exploit them to acquire skills both in gamification processes and Statistics and Big Data.

Transnational dimension

Increase in the organizational capacity of the five partner organizations and create synergies between the university, business and social sectors.

Strengthen university / business / NGO capacities, improve teacher / professional qualifications and increase student / youth competencies in statistics and bigdata

Promote the use of gamification processes in higher education and popularize the study of statistics and big data among youth and for business sectors and social

Guarantee your access to products, methodologies and creative tools for learning gamification, statistics and big data processes.

Beneficiaries

Intellectual Products

Outcomes of the project

Intellectual Products

MOOC on Gamification Processes

A MOOC on how to design, implement and evaluate gamification processes for daily teaching in higher education (especially Statistics and Big Data).

Educational Game on Statistics and Big Data

An educational game of virtual learning (through a web platform) aimed at training university students in Statistics and Big Data. This process of gamification will be a personalized training itinerary according to the competencies required by companies and social organizations in both matters

#BIGDATAFORALL

Context analysis

FOCUS GROUP

The main results obtained on **gamification** are shown below:

- Difficulty creating a game that has educational content and is fun at the same time
- The fact that everything is more interactive helps memorizing the learning content.
- Studies in Bach, and at uni see how to deal with data. Limits: It is not an entertaining subject to teach, it is not fun, interactive but it does not arouse interest. You must look for an interesting way. It is a very automatic method.

#BIGDATAFORALL

Context analysis

FOCUS GROUP

The main results obtained on **statistics and big data** are shown below:

- To interpret it, but also select the data that is most useful, why take this data and not another?
- 3 axes/difficulties: collecting data truthfully; GDPR(General Data Protection Regulation), it is necessary to know if we have authorization to process the data; tools and methodologies
- Simplify the language; Greater proximity to people's reality

#BIGDATAFORALL

Context analysis

RESULTS SURVEY

Entities Professors Students

KNOWLEDGE REQUIRE REGARDING STATISTICS AND BIG DATA

KNOWLEDGE ABOUT GAMIFICATION

#BIGDATAFORALL

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

Context analysis

RESULTS SURVEY

Context analysis

RESULTS SURVEY

Context analysis

RESULTS SURVEY

Intellectual Products

MOOC on Gamification Processes

A MOOC on how to design, implement and evaluate gamification processes for daily teaching in higher education (especially Statistics and Big Data).

Educational Game on Statistics and Big Data

An educational game of virtual learning (through a web platform) aimed at training university students in Statistics and Big Data. This process of gamification will be a personalized training itinerary according to the competencies required by companies and social organizations in both matters

#BIGDATAFORALL

Mapping: Entities

We were able to identify 46 entities, between all the partners, interested in statistics and big data.

From this mapping, we created a small report with name, sector and web address.

Web Page

Thanks for your attention!

PARTNERS

CO-FUNDED

Promoting Statistics and Big Data through Gamification and Digital Education © 2022 • COPYRIGHT

The project 2020-1-ES01-KA226-HE-095688 has been funded with support from the Erasmus+ Programme of the European Commission. This publication website reflects the views only of the author, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.